

DETERMINATION OF CRITICAL ENERGY RELEASE RATES FOR STEEL-CFRP INTERFACES CONSIDERING RESIDUAL THERMAL STRESSES

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ABSTRACT

This publication deals with the topic of experimental determination of critical energy release rates (cERR) for multi-material interfaces. Based on the experimental results the portion of the residual stresses on the fracture toughness is calculated considering an analytical solution from the literature. Especially, the combination of carbon fibre reinforced plastics with steel is investigated. Therefore, the temperature at which the bonding between the constituents takes place, the so called stress free temperature is approximately determined in a thermal test set-up. Further, Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) and End Notch Flexure (ENF) tests are conducted to determine the cERR in mode I and II. To validate the results Finite Element simulations employing the Virtual Crack Closure Technique are conducted. The investigations reveal a maximum thermal part of almost 20% on the cERR and how the thermal influence on ENF tests can be reduced.

1. MOTIVATION

In modern lightweight structures carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) are often the first choice of material, as they show a relatively high stiffness and strength in fibre directions concurrent with a low density. Beside these positive aspects some negative issues as e.g. a low damage tolerance and joining strength are related to CFRP structures. One possible solution is the combination with metal alloys to combine the positive aspects of these two material groups to so called Fibre Metal Laminates (FML). The most known hybrid material is GLARE (combination of aluminium with glass fibre epoxy), which was successfully utilized to increase the fatigue resistance in parts of the A380. To overcome the above mentioned weaknesses of CFRP -low bearing strength and damage tolerance- the combination with

titanium or steel alloys is necessary. Examples of application are the use of very thin steel layers to decrease the damage after impact [8] or the so called local metal hybridization, where locally CFRP layers are replaced to achieve a high bearing strength, while the laminate thickness is conserved [9].

Especially, the combination of CFRP and steel is accompanied by larger challenges than in case of GLARE. One major concern is the difference in the thermal expansion coefficients (CTE), which results in thermal residual stresses resulting from curing in an autoclave at high temperatures. In fibre direction the CTE is very small or can even be negative. In contrary, the steel CTE is quite large, what leads to residual tension stresses in steel foil, compression stresses in the CFRP layers and interlaminar shear stresses.

The key to success in any FML application is a good adhesion and hence the corresponding metal surface treatment. However, delaminations are the dominating failure type, when many interfaces steel to 0°layers are present as observed by Petersen et al. [13]. For composites critical energy release rates (cERR) are commonly considered to characterize the fracture toughness. They can be further used to simulate crack propagation based on the Finite Element Method (FEM).

The cERR for peel, shear or combined loading can be experimentally determined. Commonly considered tests are the Double Cantilever Beam test (DCB) for mode I and the End notched Flexure test (ENF) for mode II [4]. A combination can be realized in a mixed mode bending test [3].

When interfaces between metal and CFRP are tested the mentioned residual stresses exhibit an impact on the cERR. This paper deals with the estimation of this im-

Figure 1. Asymmetrical specimens at $T=23^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T=125^{\circ}\text{C}$

pact. Therefore, the stress free temperature is approximately determined in an experimental set-up and further employed in an analytical solution to calculate the thermal portion of the cERR.

2. MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING

In this study an austenitic cold rolled steel foil of the alloy X10CrNi18-8 is combined with the prepreg system M21/T700GC from Hexcel. The thickness of the material is $t=0.13$ mm respectively $t=0.131$. In previous studies both materials have been characterized in static tests to obtain material properties [12, 13].

The pretreatment of the steel foil can be separated into two main steps. First, vacuum grit blasting is used to remove the oxide film. Second, a patented sol-gel process is used as a coating agent [1, 6]. This pretreatment provides a good adhesion quality and is also a relative easy to handle and environmentally friendly process [14].

The materials are laid up by hand to build the laminate. To achieve constant fibre volume content, an adhesive edge dam is used and the stacked plies are wrapped in release film. Additionally, a top plate made from the same material as the bottom tooling is used to apply a homogeneous pressure. The laminate is cured in an autoclave at 180°C , which is reached by a heating ramp of 2 K/min. Further, 6 bar pressure is applied. Finally, the specimens are cut to their final geometry by a water jet.

3. ESTIMATION OF STRESS FREE TEMPERATURE

The manufacturing process of thermoset composites is characterized by the curing reaction taking place under pressure and temperature. The temperature at which the bonding between metal and CFRP takes place is the so called stress free temperature T_{SF} , what means that no stresses in the laminate are present. A conservative approach to estimate the residual stresses is to define the maximum curing temperature as T_{SF} and to apply a temperature difference between employed temperature and maximum process temperature, e.g. room temperature: $\Delta T = 180 - 23 = 157$ K. However, investigations of Prussak et al. showed that the interlaminar bonding already takes place at lower temperatures and that the transferred load during curing is depending on various parameters as curing reaction, friction between tooling and laminate and also the applied pressure [19].

A pragmatic approach to estimate T_{SF} is the investigation of asymmetrical specimens built from one layer of 0° -CFRP and one layer of steel foil [14, 19, 20]. These are manufactured in the same process as the FML structures. To avoid bending during the autoclave process two asymmetrical specimens are put together to a symmetrical layup divided by a release foil. Because of the asymmetry the specimen do not exhibit inner stresses, but show a curvature after cooling. One possibility is to

measure the curvature and use the classical laminate theory to evaluate T_{SF} . The second possibility is reheating the specimens in an oven. When T_{SF} is reached, the specimens become plane as it is shown in Fig.1.

Table 1. T_{SF} from different methods

Method	Position	MEAN [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	CoV [%]
Curvature	top (n=1)	109.6	-
	bottom (n=1)	118.6	-
Reheating	top (n=3)	124.0	2.1
	bottom (n=4)	132.3	5.9

The results in Tab.1 show lower values for direct curvature measurement than the reheating method. Also, specimens positioned on the bottom next to the tooling show higher values than specimens from the top, what might be caused by the thermal expansion of the tooling and the load transfer by friction into the uncured specimen. The here described findings were also approved by the detailed investigation of the curing reaction by fibre-bragg sensors [15].

4. FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TESTS

The manufacturing of fracture toughness specimens follows the same procedure as described in Section 2. To realize a precrack a teflon foil is inserted between the layers of the investigated interface.

5.1 Beam Theory

The principle behind the evaluation of the tests is the Bernoulli beam theory. Fig.2 Shows the basic design and parameters of the specimens and tests Parameter a is the length of an artificial precrack inside the laminates.

Figure 2. Sketch of DCB and ENF test with required input values

Fig.3 illustrates the principle behind the evaluation. In dependency on the crack length a and the corresponding bending stiffness of the specimens arms the force P causes a deflection δ and hence, a specific amount of potential energy equal the area under the curve. If crack growth occurs ($a+da$) the stiffness decreases, what means that the same force P leads to a larger displacement. The resulting difference in the potential energy ΔE is set equal to the energy which got dissipated during the crack growth and hence, is the material inherent cERR. Therefore, the energy is related to the surface of the crack growth $b*da$, with b the specimen width.

Figure 3. Evaluation principle of cERR tests

Equation (1) is used to calculate the peel mode I cERR G_{Ic} , where Eq. (2) can be used to obtain G_{IIc} for mode II.

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3P\delta}{2ba} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9Pa^2\delta}{2b*(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad (2)$$

Additionally, a Compliance Calibration method following the described methods from the standard ASTM D 5528 [2] is used to compensate nonlinearities. Here, the results of the ‘‘Corrected Beam Theory’’ (CBT) are presented.

5.2 Multidirectional and Multi-Material Interfaces

Above mentioned specimens are commonly used to investigate the fracture toughness between different layers of monolithic composites. However, if multidirectional interfaces e.g. with layers of the orientations 0//45, 0//90, 45//45 or 45//90 are investigated, occurring asymmetries lead to unwanted bending and parasitic modes. Therefore, the layups have to be chosen carefully to avoid the unwanted effects [1, 7]. Feasible layups can be found in the literature [7, 17] and the asymmetry effects can approximately be neglected.

However, effects like crack propagation through layers and crack growth in other than the desired interface are commonly occurring. Here, additional specimens with different artificial pre cracks are used to obtain the required compliance for the calibration method.

The multidirectional layups can easily be adapted to FMLs using an interface with one metal layer. It can be expected that the crack stays in the desired interface as the metal foil acts as a barrier. However, residual thermal stresses can have a large influence on the results, what is discussed in detail in this publication. The considered layups are listed in Tab.2.

Table 2. Investigated layups

Interface	Layup
0//0	[0 ₁₇ //0 ₁₇]
0//90	[(0 ₂ ,90) ₆ ,0 ₂ //90,(0 ₂ ,90) ₆ ,0 ₂]
0//45	[(0 ₂ ,90) ₆ ,0 ₂ //45,(0 ₂ ,90) ₆ ,0 ₂]
45//45	[-45, 0,(45) ₂ , 0, -45, 45, 0, (-45) ₂ , 0, 45 // -45, 0, (45) ₂ , 0, 45, -45, 0, (-45) ₂ , 0, 45

St//0	[0 ₁₆ , St//0 ₁₇]
St//90	[(0 ₂ ,90) ₆ ,0, St//90,(0 ₂ ,90) ₆ ,0 ₂]
St//45	[(0 ₂ ,90) ₆ ,0, St//45,(0 ₂ ,90) ₆ ,0 ₂]

5. INFLUENCE OF THERMAL STRESSES

An analytical solution to calculate the portion of the cERR, which is related to a thermal loading was presented by Nairn [11] and can be employed in a formulation by Yokozeki [21] for DCB, ENF and MMB tests. Here, the solutions for DCB and ENF tests are presented in Eqs.3 and 4.

$$G_{Ic}^{total} = G_{Ic}^{mech} + \frac{P\Delta T}{b} (\alpha_{\kappa}^{(1)} - \alpha_{\kappa}^{(2)})a + \frac{(\Delta T)^2}{2b} (I^{(1)} + I^{(2)} - I^{(3)}) \quad (3)$$

$$G_{IIc}^{total} = G_{IIc}^{mech} + \frac{P\Delta T}{2b} (\alpha_{\kappa}^{(2)} - \alpha_{\kappa}^{(3)})a + \frac{(\Delta T)^2}{2b} (I^{(1)} + I^{(2)} - I^{(3)}) \quad (4)$$

The specimens are divided into three sublaminates $k=1,2,3$, representing the two separated arms and the unseparated part. Following parameters are defined:

$$\alpha_{\kappa}^{(k)} = \frac{D_{11}^k * N_T^k - B_{11}^k * M_T^k}{A_{11}^k * D_{11}^k - B_{11}^k} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\alpha_{\kappa}^{(k)} = \frac{A_{11}^k * M_T^k - B_{11}^k * N_T^k}{A_{11}^k * D_{11}^k - B_{11}^k} \quad (6)$$

are the CTEs of the sublaminates. The thermal loading portions are

$$N_T^{(k)} = b \sum_{i=1}^k E_i^k \alpha_i^k (z_i^k - z_{i-1}^k) \quad (7)$$

and

$$M_T^{(k)} = \frac{1}{2} b \sum_{i=1}^k E_i^k \alpha_i^k (z_i^{k,2} - z_{i-1}^{k,2}) \quad (8)$$

leading to

$$I^k = N_T^k * \alpha_{\kappa}^k + M_T^k * \alpha_{\kappa}^k - b \sum_{i=1}^k E_i^k \alpha_i^{k,2} t_i^k \quad (9)$$

Herein i is the lamina index. Values like the elasticities E or the entries of the ABD-matrix A_{11} , B_{11} or D_{11} are well known parameters from the classical laminate theory and t is the lamina thickness.

6. DETERMINATION OF CRITICAL ENERGY RELEASE RATES

Fig.4 shows the DCB test set-up. To record the values for the CBT the applied force is displayed using an analogue signal and a voltmeter. This enables the required synchronization between load/displacement and crack propagation by a camera recording.

Figure 4. DCB test set-up

A simpler conduction is related to the ENF test set-up. It represents a 3-point bending set-up, where the moment induces the shear loading in the interface of a cracked laminate.

The results of the monolithic DCB specimens are depicted in Fig.6. An interface $0^\circ//0^\circ$ exhibits the lowest fracture toughness and interfaces $0^\circ//90^\circ$ and $45^\circ//45^\circ$ the highest values accompanied by the highest scatter.

Figure 5. DCB results of CFRP specimens obtained with corrected beam theory

The results of the monolithic ENF tests in Fig.6 do not show as large differences as the DCB tests and the scatter is much smaller. However, again the $0//0$ interface shows the smallest fracture toughness.

Figure 6. ENF results of CFRP specimens

Fig.7 depicts the test results of the hybrid DCB speci-

mens. The experimentally obtained values are smaller than in case of the monolithic specimens. One reason lies in the residual stresses. These have to be added to the mechanical loading. The DCB test provides a symmetrical bending loading on both specimens' arms, leading to a tension strain on the inner layers next to the crack tip, which is superposed with the thermal tension strain in the steel layer. Hence, the true mechanical value would be higher than measured in the experiment.

Figure 7. DCB results of CFRP specimens obtained with corrected beam theory with thermal portion

In contrary, the thermal portion in the ENF tests is acting against the mechanical loading and has to be subtracted from the experimental value as can be seen in Fig.8. Additionally, the orientation of the specimen – metal foil on upper or bottom side of crack- plays an important role. If the metal foil is positioned on the upper side, the thermal portion can be reduced. Following this procedure, coincidence can be achieved for the test series with steel layers and 0° -plies. Here, the thermal portion is 19% of the experimental value.

However, for the series with steel and 45° -layers the effect is visible, but does not lead to coincidence. The maximum thermal portion is also about 20% of the experimental value. The test series St/90° was tested only with the intention to minimize the thermal portion. At all, the hybrid test series do not show the same trend as the monolithic series.

Figure 8. ENF results of hybrid specimens with thermal portion; St//0° = top//bottom side of interface

Figure 10. Load-displacement curves of 0//0 and 0//45 DCB simulation

7. NUMERICAL VALIDATION

To simulate the growth of an already existing crack the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) is a feasible method and used to validate the experimentally obtained results [10]. Hereby, the energy release rates G are calculated with the displacements at nodes before the closed crack and forces at the crack tip as depicted in Fig.9.

Figure 9. Scheme of VCCT

The calculation of the ERR in Mode I and II is conducted with following equations:

$$G_I = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} [F_{zi} * \Delta u_{zj}] \quad (10)$$

respectively

$$G_{II} = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} [F_{xi} * \Delta u_{xi}] \quad (11)$$

Crack opening occurs when the criterion in Eq. 12 is satisfied

$$G/G_c \geq 1 \quad (12)$$

The test specimens are modelled with 3D solid elements and a nonlinear implicit simulation is conducted. To include the effect of the thermal stresses a global temperature load case of $\Delta T \approx -100$ K is applied based on the results in section 3.

As shown in Fig.10 the load displacement curves of simulation and test are compared under the aspect of initial stiffness, start of nonlinearity and maximum

force. If no crack jumping occurs as in case of 0//0 or the hybrid specimens the VCCT is a feasible method to simulate the test results. On the contrary, if crack jumping occurs as in case of multidirectional interfaces the behaviour cannot be described by this method. However, the beginning of the nonlinearity can be predicted quite accurately.

Fig.11 shows the results of DCB simulation with specimens of the interface 0//St. If the experimentally obtained value of G_{Ic} is employed the maximum occurring force of the experiments and the simulation are almost coincident. However, if the by the amount of the residual stresses corrected value in combination with the temperature load case is applied, the obtained maximum force is slightly lower. The inspection of the crack front formation shows an early growth from the edges, what seems to be the reason for the difference.

Figure 11. Results of DCB simulation with 0//St interface for different cERR with and without ΔT

8. CONCLUSION

The cERR for multidirectional and multi-material interfaces in Mode I and II are determined with the described procedure. The thermal portion contributes or hinders the crack occurrence in dependency to the load case.

Additionally, to the here investigated fracture modes the interaction should be investigated in a MMB test.

The determination of the thermal portion is necessary if the effect of residual stresses on the interlaminar as well the intralaminar properties have to be investigated and a global temperature load case is applied. Otherwise the effect on the interlaminar properties is already considered in the experimentally determined cERR values and can solely be used in the analysis if only delamination as failure type is taken into account.

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